

Version 1	Created by Liz Guzman-Ramirez 03/03/2022
Version 2	Created by Joanna Mania 12/09/2024, revised by Anna Volkova 26/09/2024
Version 3	Added a question: where will the data be stored during the research? Joanna Mania 28/11/2024, revised by Anna Volkova 1-12-2024, reviewed by Eduard Klapwijk 19-12-2024

NWO Grant Application – Research Data Management Section

Below, you will find basic background information to all parts of the NWO data management paragraph, including an overview of options available at Erasmus University Rotterdam. If you have questions/concerns, please, consult your [faculty research data steward](#) and/or [privacy officer \(for research involving personal data\)](#).

What does NWO mean by ‘research data’?

- **Evidence underlying the answer to research questions** that can be used to **validate research findings**.
- Data can be **quantitative** information or **qualitative** statements, collected by researchers through **experiments, observations, models, interviews or other methods, or information derived from existing scientific evidence**.
- In addition:
 - o digital information obtained by analysing physical objects (such as scientific or archaeological collections, physical artworks or biobanks)
 - o software (algorithms, scripts and code developed by researchers during their work), if needed to interpret data

These texts are only examples. When making use of the examples, choose what is relevant to the type of data collected in your project and rephrase!

Q1. Will this project involve re-using existing research data?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: Are there any constraints on its re-use?	
<p>Example explanation</p> <p>Example: use of CBS data</p> <p><i>“We will be reusing CBS data, all the pseudonymized aggregated data is publicly available to use but the raw data cannot be shared to protect the participant’s personal information. We will direct readers to the CBS data sources where possible (for example via the ODISSEI CBS portal). “</i></p> <p>Example: reuse of anonymized data from data repository</p> <p><i>“In our project, we are going to retrieve openly available datasets on migration (years 1980-2020) from DANS, ICSPR and Barometer. Datasets are anonymized. We will follow the use permission specified in the data licence (preference for CC0 or CC-BY) and credit creators where necessary.”</i></p> <p>Example: archival data</p> <p><i>“Data used for WP2 and WP3 will be collected in the archives of the Rijksmuseum. Reuse and reproduction of this data is restrained by the access conditions, that researchers must sign. Reproduction rights of images might be restricted by copyrights. We will seek separate permission from the Rijksmuseum to use the archival materials in scientific publications.”</i></p>	Additional notes
<input type="checkbox"/> No: Have you considered re-using existing data but discarded the possibility? Why?	
<p>Example explanation</p> <p>Example: data does not exist</p> <p><i>“The data that we need to answer the research question does not exist, therefore we need to collect the information ourselves.”</i></p>	Additional notes

<p>Example: data incomplete <i>“Work on the WP2 builds partially on existing data (on Bavaria, Catalonia, Basque, Brittany), however, those datasets miss data on geographical regions (Corsica, Istria, Upper Silesia) that are essential for our project. Our data collection will therefore focus on filling in those gaps by using a similar methodology.”</i></p>	
Q1/Q2. Will data be collected or generated that are suitable for reuse?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: Please answer questions 3 and 4.	
<input type="checkbox"/> No: Please explain why the research will not result in reusable data or in data that cannot be stored or data that for other reasons are not relevant for reuse.	
<p>Example explanation Example: web scraping <i>“For our research we will be using data scraped from social media. Due to restrictive terms of use, we are not allowed to share the data. However, we will share the query used to retrieve the data.”</i></p> <p>Example: sensitive data, NDA <i>“Findings generated within WP4 are based on proprietary data provided by Philips B.V. Due to the sensitive nature of the data, academic partners sign an NDA which fully restricts the possibility to share and publish data.”</i></p>	<p>Additional notes</p>
Q2. Where will the data be stored during the research?	
<p>Example explanation Example: using storage available at EUR <i>“Research data will be stored in Yoda, a cloud-based storage solution provided by EUR, within a closed user group, accessible to authorized users only. The access to the storage will be managed by the PI or the person responsible for the data management. The researchers involved in the project will discuss and agree on the folder structure and naming conventions that match the nature of the project and data. The data will be backed-up on a regular basis to prevent accidental loss.”</i></p>	<p>Additional notes EUR researchers can make use of data storage facilities provided by our institution. See Tooling page.</p>
Q3. After the project has been completed, [...] Please state these here.	
... how will the data be stored for the long-term and made available for the use by third parties?	
<p>Example explanation Example: quantitative data, reusable package <i>“Each scientific publication will come with a reusable data package for verification purposes and transparency. These packages will be deposited in the DANS data repository* together with a DOI and metadata. Quantitative data packages (WP2, WP3) will consist of processed datasets, analysis script in Python or SPSS, variable codebook, questionnaire, and a readme file. They will be published open access under a CC-BY licence**.”</i></p> <p>Example: qualitative data, reusable package, archival package <i>“For the long-term, the data will be stored in the Erasmus Data Repository, which makes my research findable, citable, and reusable for others. In this repository, datasets containing no personal information (e.g. codebooks, mindmaps, certain fieldnotes, memos) will be shared open access. Open access will be granted as part of a CC BY licence, which allows to reuse, mix, and merge my data as long as I am credited. Datasets containing personal information (e.g. interview transcripts, screenshots, community meeting notes) will be de-identified, stored in a separate location, and controlled with restricted access for reasons of scientific integrity. This can be done in EUR Yoda Vault for a period of 10+ years under password protection.”</i></p> <p>Example: archival package 1 <i>“In addition, we will prepare archival packages that will be stored internally in the institutional archive*** EUR Yoda Vault for 10 years. They will include raw data containing personal data, contracts, DMPs, letters of ethics approval, funding agreements, and other project documentation.”</i></p> <p>Example: archival package 2 <i>“At the end of each sub-project, the PI will submit archival package to the institutional archive. It will include video recordings, signed informed consent forms, manuscript and all additional documentation needed to verify that sub-project.”</i></p>	<p>Additional notes Following the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, at the end of the project researchers should create 2 packages: a reusable data package and an archival package.</p> <p>*data repositories: EUR Data Repository (institutional) DANS Data Stations (SSH) Zenodo (general-purpose) OSF (general- purpose) Other fields</p> <p>**most encouraged by NWO: CC0 – no copyright CC-BY – requires only attribution Other CC licences</p> <p>***institutional archive EUR Yoda Vault (EUR archive)</p>

... are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?	
<p>Example: privacy restriction, qualitative data <i>“Despite applying pseudonymization techniques to the interview data, the access to the interview transcripts will be restricted to provide an additional level of protection for participants and their data. Metadata will contain all necessary information on how to request access to data. Access to that data will be evaluated and granted case-by-case. Data sharing agreements will need to be in place before sharing data. All other research materials and instruments (interview guides, interview questions, blank informed consent, analysis codebook) will be published open access under a CC-BY licence.”</i></p> <p>Example: embargo <i>“Data will become publicly available as soon as the article is accepted for publication.”</i></p> <p>Example: proprietary data <i>“Unilever data used in sub-study 3 is of commercial value, therefore it cannot be made available for reuse. We will create a synthetic dataset that could be used to replicate the results.”</i></p>	<p>Possible restrictions to data sharing: GDPR, IPR, commercial value, proprietary data</p>
4. Will any costs (financial and time) related to data management and sharing/preservation be incurred?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: Then please be sure to specify the associated expenses in the budget table of this proposal.	
<p>Example explanation</p> <p>Example: documentation, anonymization, transcription <i>“A budget is allocated for transcription services (50h of Amberscript, xxx euro). In addition, we will hire a student assistant to anonymize interviews and document data (64h, 1088 euro)”.</i></p> <p>Example: data storage, research software developers <i>“In our project, we will collect and process high volumes of data, therefore an extra budget is allocated for additional storage space and support of research software developers”</i></p>	<p>Additional notes</p> <p>Extra costs related to data management are: anonymization, converting file formats, file digitization, documentation, data cleaning, data storage (for large datasets), transcription, research software developers. For more information on costs related to data management, please see this webpage. Data management costs fall under the budget module ‘material budget’.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> No: All the necessary resources (financial and time) to store and prepare data for sharing/preservation are or will be available at no extra cost.	
<p>Example explanation</p> <p>Example: in-house expertise <i>“All necessary resources and expertise to prepare, store and archive data (e.g. data management planning, storage solutions, privacy officer, trainings and workshops, ethics review boards) are available at no extra costs at EUR.”</i></p>	<p>List of facilities/services available at no extra-cost at EUR:</p> <p>Faculty privacy officers (GDPR, privacy impact assessment, data processing agreements). Faculty research data stewards (data management, storage, policies, tools, archive, DMP)</p> <p>Faculty legal counsels (contracts, legal issues)</p> <p>EDSC (Erasmus Data Service Centre) (access to databases, expertise in research data)</p> <p>EUR/Faculty Internal Review Board (ethical approval of research)</p>

